

THE CONCEPT AND FUNCTIONS OF COMPETITION

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Annotation: *The article discusses the concepts and issues of competition in a market economy, explanations are explained by examples. In addition, the features of competition are described.*

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The modern market economy is a complex organism, consisting of a huge number of various industrial, commercial, financial and information structures interacting against the backdrop of an extensive system of economic and legal norms, and united by a single concept - the market. [1].

Market competitiveness is determined by the limits in which individual firms are able to influence the market, i.e., the conditions for the sale of their products, primarily prices. The less influence individual firms have on the market in which they sell their products, the more competitive the market is considered to be. The highest degree of market competition is achieved when an individual firm has absolutely no influence on it. This is possible only when there are so many firms operating on the commodity market that each of them, in particular, cannot influence the price of the commodity in any way, and perceives it as such, determined by market demand and supply. Such a market is called fully competitive. [2]

Competition is one of the strongest incentives for the revitalization of economic activity, the main lever for accelerating scientific and technological progress and the search for progressive forms of labor organization, the main condition for increasing the efficiency and quality of work. The absence of competition cannot be replaced by directives, wage differentiation, or other economic incentives. [1]

The practical elimination of natural economic competition in a non-market economy does not give it a chance to reach the level of efficiency of a market economy.

Competition in the broad sense of the word means competitive, rival relations between two or more economic entities, participants in economic activity, manifested in the desire of each of them to bypass the others in achieving a common goal, to get a better result, to push the rival aside. Competition is a special kind of honest economic struggle, in which, if there are in principle equal chances for each of the

parties claiming success, the more skillful, enterprising, capable side, which makes better use of its capabilities, finds ways to outstrip or push back, oust the enemy.

Thus, modern competition is not depriving others of the opportunity to achieve the desired benefits, goals, results and not achieving them at the expense of others, but the use of adequate opportunities in a better way, due to which a higher result is achieved.

Competition in its sports analogy is most likely not like boxing, but a running competition, when the winner is the one who has higher energy, skill, endurance, knows how to better use his chances, and does not push opponents off the treadmill. But, as in sports, in competition the success of some is the failure of others. There is no escape from this, without it there can be no competition. *Competition features.* To survive in the struggle, the entrepreneur must offer products that the consumer prefers (consumer sovereignty). Consequently, the factors of production, under the influence of price, are directed to those industries where they are most needed motivation function [4]. For an entrepreneur, competition means chance and risk at the same time:

- enterprises offering higher quality products or producing them with lower production costs are rewarded in the form of profits (positive sanctions). This stimulates technological progress;
- Businesses that do not respond to consumer wishes or violations of competition rules by their competitors in the market are penalized in the form of losses or forced out of the market (negative sanctions).

Distribution function. Competition not only includes incentives to increase productivity, but also allows income to be distributed among businesses and households according to their efficient contribution.

Control function. Competition restricts and controls economic power of each enterprise. For example, a monopolist may set a price. At the same time, competition provides the buyer with the opportunity to choose among several sellers. The more perfect the competition, the fairer the price [5].

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that economic competition is useful and effective only when the desire to get ahead of the opponent turns into a desire to improve the quality and effectiveness of one's own activities. Since in conditions of normal competition all competing entities strive for success, regardless of the luck of those who are ahead and those who are behind, there is general progress, general success - everyone is trying to improve their performance.

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